

Nutrient use efficiency and upland rice yield

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Eastern Uttar Pradesh is a major rice growing area which often has drought that makes rice culture risky. Average rainfall is about 1,000 mm, but distribution is erratic.

A field experiment in sandy loam soils to determine varietal response to added nitrogen was conducted in 1976 and repeated in 1978 at Faizabad. Eleven semi-dwarf and tall rice varieties were grown at 0, 20, 40, 60, and 80 kg N/ha. Phosphorus (13 kg/ha) and potassium (25 kg/ha) were applied at sowing. Nitrogen was applied basally in two equal splits at sowing and tillering. Plots were direct-seeded at 100 kg/ha in rows 20 cm apart after the first rains in July. Figure 1 shows weekly rainfall distribution during the two seasons.

Grain yield in 1976 increased at all nitrogen application levels. IET826 (3.3 t/ha) yielded highest, followed by IET2918 (3.0 t/ha) and FH109 (2.8 t/ha). N22 and Brown Gora yielded 2.5 and 2.4 t/ha. Other variety yields were intermediate.

In 1978 IET826 (2.6 t/ha) yielded

1. Distribution pattern of rainfall at Faizabad, India, 1976 and 1978.

highest, followed by IET1444 (Rasi) (2.5 t/ha). N22 had the lowest yield – 2.1 t/ha.

Nutrient use efficiency (NUE) was calculated for each genotype by dividing the quantity of additional grain yield produced by the nitrogen applied (Fig. 2).

IET826 and IET1444 (Rasi) had a high NUE curve; IET2918, IET2912, Brown Gora, KR-5-142, and Cauvery had a medium NUE curve; and IET3226, FH109, N22, and IET2232 (Narendra 1) had a low curve. □

2. Nutrient use efficiency (NUE) trends of selected upland rice strains, Faizabad, India, 1976 and 1978.

Growth rate of azolla in Colombia

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Azolla quickly adapted to simulated in situ conditions when transferred from slow-growing maintenance or storage cultures. Although storage cultures had near-stationary growth rate, the azolla achieved normal growth rate within a week after transfer into simulated environments.

Six of 11 Colombian isolates of *Azolla filiculoides* (provisional designation) were tested at the University of Florida, Gainesville. During the first week after transfer, most isolates doubled fresh

weight (FW) in 2 days and dry weight (DW) in less than 72 hours, when grown at moderate light levels (15 klux, 18-hour days) and temperature (26°C day, 22°C night) (Table 1). Doubling increased to 3 days for FW and 4 days for DW the second week after inoculation, probably because of crowding.

Growth rate of the storage culture inoculum, and the conditions of the storage environment affected turnover time and final biomass harvests. In Monteria-3 FW doubling average was 3.20 times and the DW doubling was 3.41 times during the first 7 days of the growth test when the inoculum

Table 1. Isolate doubling times.

Isolate	Doubling time (days)			
	1 wk		2 wk	
	FW	DW	FW	DW
Monteria-2	2.40 ± 0.44	2.26 ± 0.35	2.45 ± 0.20	2.81 ± 0.30
Monteria-3	2.17 ± 0.11	2.11 ± 0.08	3.36 ± 0.24	4.23 ± 0.22
CIAT	2.00 ± 0.04	2.06 ± 0.06	—	—
Amazon-C	1.92 ± 0.27	1.96 ± 0.21	—	—
Amazon-R	2.01 ± 0.11	1.93 ± 0.13	3.22 ± 0.54	4.24 ± 0.99
Amazon-Y	1.96 ± 0.21	1.88 ± 0.14	3.33 ± 0.28	3.85 ± 0.46

was obtained from an in vitro culture with a high growth rate (trial 1). FW doubling was reduced to 3.06 times and DW 3.25 times when the inoculum was obtained from storage cultures with a minimal growth rate (trial 2). FW doubling fell to 3.14 times and DW to 2.94 times when the inoculum came from storage cultures with near-stationary growth rate, that had been subjected to very low (less than 10 klux) light intensities (trial 3).

Regardless of preinoculation conditions, the growth rate of this isolate (FW measurement) showed an initial lag phase followed by an increase during the first 7 days of the trial. During FW growth rate increase, growth rate determined by DW was decreased correspondingly. At 7 days, the DW and FW growth rates were similar (Table 2).

Another azolla isolate, Amazon-R, was

Table 2. Daily growth rates of *Monterita*-3.

Time lapse	Daily growth rate					
	Trial 1 ^a		Trial 2 ^b		Trial 3 ^c	
	FW	DW	FW	DW	FW	DW
1-day	0.24 ± 0.06	0.54	0	0.39 ± 0.14	0	0.47 ± 0.24
2-day	0.53 ± 0.01	0.69 ± 0.08	0.07 ± 0.06	0.26 ± 0.13	0.21 ± 0.07	0.43 ± 0.10
3-day	0.43 ± 0.02	0.58 ± 0.04	0.37 ± 0.07	0.55 ± 0.10	0.40 ± 0.05	0.52 ± 0.03
4-day	—	—	—	—	0.38 ± 0.06	0.51 ± 0.04
5-day	—	—	—	—	0.43 ± 0.08	0.46 ± 0.07
6-day	—	—	—	—	0.46 ± 0.02	0.47 ± 0.03
7-day	0.46 ± 0.02	0.48 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.03	0.47 ± 0.02	0.44 ± 0.05	0.44 ± 0.02
14day	0.30 ± 0.02	0.24 ± 0.02	—	—	0.33 ± 0.02	0.29 ± 0.02

^aTrial 1: no difference between storage and growth trial conditions. ^bTrial 2: inoculum not in active growth phase. ^cTrial 3: inoculum not in active growth and stored under < 10 klux.

incubated for 24 hours under stress parameters (darkness, 35°C). Subsequent FW diurnal growth rate remained consistently depressed (0.33) for 2 weeks. DW rate decreased 0.56 to 0.38 in 1 week, and to 0.27 in 2 weeks. Nonstressed replications showed a stable FW rate (0.54 to 0.53) and a higher, albeit decreasing, DW rate

(0.63-0.49) in the first week. At 2 weeks FW (0.31) and the DW (0.31) growth rates resembled those of the stressed replications. Total doublings were 2.24 FW and 2.67 DW after 7 days for stressed samples, and 3.73 FW and 3.43 DW for nonstressed ones. □

Differential tolerance of rices for low-sulfur soils

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Forty-three lines or varieties were studied for reaction to low-sulfur soils in irrigated fields during the wet season in South Sulawesi. Soil at the test site was a Typic Tropaquept with H 6 2, 2.66% organic matter, 4.2 µg SO₄²⁻-S/kg, 23 mmol cation exchange capacity/kg, and clay loam texture.

Entries were grown in unreplicated treated and untreated plots. Eighty kg S/ha as ammonium sulfate was applied to the treated plot, and 100 N, 26 P, and 50 K kg/ha were applied to both plots. Each entry was planted in four 3-m-long rows at 20 × 20 cm spacing.

Plant height, tiller number, days to maturity, and grain yield per hill varied by variety. Marked differences were observed in grain yield per hill and days to maturity. Using those parameters, the 43 entries were divided into 4 groups: similar grain yield and days to maturity for both treatments, different grain yield and similar days to maturity, similar grain yield

Reaction of some rice lines or varieties to low-sulfur soil by grain yield and days to maturity.

Line or variety	Grain yield (g/hill)		Days to maturity	
	+S	-S	+S	-S
Similar yield, maturity				
IR34	74.2	67.9	131	135
IR2070-24-1-5-1	56.2	49.6	131	135
Pulu bolong	36.1	33.8	147	149
Ase lelling	50.4	50.9	149	149
Mean of 9 lines or varieties	52.9	51.8	136	138
Similar yield, different maturity				
IR20	75.7	71.1	119	133
IR.2307-233-3	62.1	61.1	117	135
SPR6726-76-2-3	50.8	51.1	115	126
Pelita I/1	76.7	70.7	128	135
Mean of 9 lines or varieties	61.0	61.8	121	134
Different yield, similar maturity				
IR28	60.8	34.5	112	115
IR30	73.7	40.6	112	115
IR36	63.6	51.8	112	115
Banda	79.8	33.4	159	161
Mean of 12 lines or varieties	59.5	38.3	131	133
Different yield, maturity				
1132153-26-3-5-4	64.2	48.9	115	131
B2376-9-1	80.9	61.3	115	128
B462c-Pn-1-3	66.0	41.5	117	126
Syntha	78.0	59.3	128	140
Mean of 13 lines or varieties	62.9	42.6	118	132

and different days to maturity, and different grain yield and days to maturity (see table). Treated and Untreated plots were considered different when they

varied by at least 15% in yield and 7 days in maturity. Results suggest that rices have different reactions to low-S soil in terms of the plant parameters measured.